

The influence of Price Strategy, Trustworthiness, and Service Quality on Satisfaction and Its Impact on Words of Mouth Moderated by Status in Family Members of the Umrah Congregation of Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera Surabaya

Author's Details:

Echwan Siswadi¹, Andi Sularso², Hotman Panjaitan³

Correspondence email address: ibs.tour2@gmail.com

⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾⁽³⁾Economics and Business, August 17, 1945 Surabaya University, Indonesia

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out about pricing strategies, trustworthiness, and service quality which influence satisfaction and WOM being moderated by status in the family. The population of 1618 consumers who have traveled Umrah, 2019. Using the Slovin formula with a tolerance of 5%, the number of samples is 321 respondents.

The results showed that: 1). Pricing strategies influence customer satisfaction, and consumer WOM. 2). Trust influences consumer satisfaction. 3). Service quality has an effect on customer satisfaction, and customer satisfaction. 4). Satisfaction has a significant effect on consumer consumers. 5). Status in the family moderates the relationship of satisfaction with the WOM consumer Umrah travel agency and the Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera.

The practical implications that pricing, trust and quality of service strategies can increase customer satisfaction, which in turn will increase consumer WOM. Thus, the management needs to pay attention and increase the value of service quality, which can be done with innovative services from what has been done now. Provide schedule departure information in a timely manner, provide an adequate place of service, and others that make participants feel comfortable. Future studies are recommended to investigate further by adding other variables that have not been included in this study. Because there are many other variables that can affect word of mouth.

Keywords: price strategy, trust, service quality, satisfaction, consumer WOM.

1. Introduction

The longer the waiting list that must be accepted by the Muslim community in Indonesia who want to make the pilgrimage, making the pilgrimage to be used as an alternative option that is most popular. Apart from the price that is cheaper than the pilgrimage. Umrah worship also has a more flexible implementation time in terms of the duration of the implementation of the pilgrimage and can be done at any time. Although not as large as the pilgrimage, the pilgrimage requires funding and relatively large attention, mental readiness and excellent physical health, and relatively long implementation time. In such conditions, coupled with the many choices of Umrah and Hajj travel agencies that can meet their needs, causing prospective pilgrims will be very selective in choosing an Umrah and Hajj travel agency. Prospective pilgrims want the maximum value, limited by search costs, limited knowledge, mobility and income. They form an expectation of value, and act on it. What is the reality offered by an Umrah and Hajj travel agency to meet the expectations of pilgrims will determine the satisfaction of pilgrims. Therefore they will choose an Umrah and Hajj travel agency that will give the highest score to him.

Harumi (2016), proves the influence of trust on satisfaction. Harumi also proved the influence of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty, which in this study WOM. While Putri (2016), proved the influence of trust on satisfaction, and repurchase. Anik (2013), proves the influence of service quality, price, and customer satisfaction on WOM. Taghizadeh et al. (2012), proving the effect of satisfaction on consumer WOM.

The Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera is one of the Umrah and Hajj travel tour operators, until in 2019 it dispatched thousands of pilgrims to perform the pilgrimage. The quality of services and services after the pilgrims perform the pilgrimage are very highlighted in order to increase customer satisfaction.

Cronin, and Taylor (1994) in their research succeeded in proving that customer satisfaction is determined by customer ratings of the quality of service provided. The research results of Akbar et al. (2010) show that revitalizing service quality has a positive effect on customer loyalty. From some of the research results that have been mentioned, there has been no research linking the status of the family to the

satisfaction or to word of mouth, especially research on the travel agency Umrah and Hajj. In this study, the use of status in the family as one of the moderator variables, which will moderate the relationship of satisfaction with word of mouth is something new.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis

Consumer behavior is a long process of a person in obtaining Hasan's goods or services (2013). Consumer behavior is the process and activities of someone who is involved in finding, choosing, buying, using, evaluating, and managing products or services to meet their needs and desires. In this sense consumer behavior is associated with meeting the needs and desires. At the same goods and service needs, the desires of each consumer can differ according to the criteria and expectations of each consumer. The decision to buy a product will begin with the following steps: introduction of needs, time, situation changes, product ownership, product consumption, individual differences, marketing influence, information search, internal search, and external search.

2.1 Pricing Strategy

To be successful in marketing an item or service, every company must set its price appropriately. Price is the only element of the marketing mix that provides income and income for the company, while the three elements (product, distribution, and promotion) cause costs (expenses). Besides that, the price is a mixture element that is flexible, meaning that it can be changed quickly unlike the case with product characteristics or commitment to distribution channels. The last two things cannot be changed / adjusted easily and quickly, because they usually involve long-term decisions (Kotler, 2015).

2.2 Trust

Trust has an important role in building relationships between consumers and providers of goods or services. Consumer trust is consumer knowledge about an object, its attributes and benefits where the object can be in the form of a product, person, company, or anything with which a person has the beliefs and attitudes of Mowen and Minor (2006); Sangadji and Sopiah (2013). There are two kinds of attributes, namely intrinsic attributes related to the actual nature of the product and extrinsic attributes obtained from the external aspects of the product, such as brand names, packaging and labels. Trust is also related to attitudes, behavior and product attributes. Sumarwan (2011), states that the formation of consumer attitudes often illustrates the relationship between trust, attitude and behavior. Trust, attitude and behavior are also related to the concept of product attributes where consumers usually have confidence in product attributes.

2.3 Service quality

Service quality is a statement of attitude, the relationship resulting from the comparison between expectations and performance. Another definition of service quality is a measure of the extent to which a given service can meet customer expectations (Lupiyoadi, 2014). Panjaitan et al. (2019), states that the quality of service is an effort to meet the needs and desires of customers and the accuracy of delivery to balance customer expectations.

2.4 Customer satisfaction

Satisfaction is the overall evaluation of the customer for the performance of an offer. The concept of satisfaction varies by marketing experts, but the many concepts that are all interconnected. Oliver (1989); Supranto (2011), states that satisfaction is the level of one's feelings after comparing the performance he feels with his expectations. If the results of an evaluation of the product or service meet or exceed expectations, then the customer will be positive towards the company and wish to buy back the same product or service or even more than that by acting to refer to others. Basically satisfaction becomes an important role in explaining why customers become loyal to a product or service offered by the company.

2.5 Status in family

In making consumer purchasing decisions, families have strategic influence. Schiffman (2010), states that families as 2 or more people are related by blood relations, marriage, or adoption who live together. The same thing was expressed by Virmani and Sharma (1993), which defines the family as two or more people who are related by blood, marriage, or adoption and live together.

2.6. Word Of Mouth

Word of mouth communication, basically is a message about a company's product or service, or about the company itself, in the form of comments about product performance, friendliness, honesty, speed of service and other things that are felt and experienced by someone delivered to others. The message delivered can take the form of messages that are positive or negative depending on what is felt by the message provider for the services he consumes. In this paper the behavioral construct of Wom refers to the concept of Oliver, and Swan (1989); Walker (2011).

2.7 Theoretical Framework

The relationship between the variables used is seen as Figure. 1 and each relationship of the independent variable with the dependent variable represent the hypothesis.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The research hypothesis is as follows:

1. Price strategy has a significant effect on customer satisfaction
2. Price strategy has a significant effect on consumer WOM
3. Trust has a significant effect on customer satisfaction
4. Service quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction
5. Service quality has a significant effect on consumer WOM
6. Satisfaction has a significant effect on consumer WOM
7. Status in the family significantly moderates the relationship of satisfaction with WOM consumers Umrah travel agency and the Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera

3. Research methods

This research is causal explanatory research, which will prove the causal relationship between variables. The population is all consumers who have traveled Umrah using the Ichwan Berkah Sejahtera travel agency,

in 2019, as many as 1618 worshipers. Referring to the Slovin formula with a tolerance of 5%, the number of samples is 321 respondents, with SEM analysis.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Characteristics of Respondents

Respondents selected as samples in this study were generally 34-71 years old, and most were in the 46-55 years age group. The number of respondents included in the 25-35 year age group was 01.5% (5 respondents), the number of respondents included in the 36-45 year age group was 20.0% (64 respondents), the 46-55 year age group was 42, 2% (145 respondents), and age groups > 55 years were 33.3% (107 respondents). Respondents male sex 43.9%, as many as 141 people while women consisted of 56.1%, namely as many as 181 respondents. Description of respondents based on the level of study most of the respondents were participants of the Umrah and Hajj pilgrimage tour who graduated from high school as many as 39 respondents (21.1%). With a diploma certificate, as many as 155 respondents (48.3%). Those with a Bachelor's degree were 111 respondents (34.6%) of the total respondents. Description based on profession, most of the respondents, were entrepreneurs, as many as 126 respondents (39.3%). The second largest group of respondents is the merchant respondent group, which is 101 respondents (31.5%). The rests are farmers and other profession respondents, 94 respondents (29.3%) of the total respondents.

4.2 Instrument Testing Results

The results of validity testing show significantly for all indicators or items in question, which means that the indicator or question items for each variable included in the questionnaire have met the validity requirements. From the Pearson product moment correlation results, it is known that all items in question on the questionnaire correlate significantly with an error rate of 5% (** < 0.05), so it can be said that all items in question are valid and can be further processed. The reliability test results with the Cronbach alpha test (α) in this study indicate that all the variables of this study are reliable, because all alpha coefficient values of each variable are greater than standardized research (0.6), so each question item on the measurement instrument can be used. A correlation value of the total items corrected for all items in question is greater than 0.3.

4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the research measurement model based on the results of the statistical test, obtained the loading factor value for each indicator that forms a research variable greater than 3, therefore, all indicators of the research variables are indicators that significantly shape each research variable.

Table 1: Analisis Faktor Konfirmatori

Research variables	Relationship	C. R.	Loading Factor (λ)	Probability
Strategi harga	Harga → harg1	2,000	0,776	0,000
	Harga → harg2	13,335	0,847	0,000
	Harga → harg3	13,253	0,839	0,000
	Harga → harg4	8,723	0,552	0,000
Kepercayaan	Trust → trs1	2,000	0,733	0,000
	Trust → trs2	7,116	0,712	0,000
	Trust → trs3	7,017	0,596	0,000
	Trust → trs4	2,376	0,480	0,000
Kualitas Pelayanan	Kual → kual1	2,000	0,623	0,000
	Kual → kual2	9,321	0,981	0,000
	Kual → kual3	8,389	0,581	0,000

	Kual → kual4	4,620	0,303	0,000
	Kual → kual5	6,636	0,444	0,000
Status dalam Keluarga	Status → sts1	2,000	0,369	0,000
	Status → sts2	4,232	0,619	0,000
Kepuasan	Status → sts3	3,724	0,742	0,000
	Ipuas → puas1	2,000	0,627	0,000
	Ipuas → puas2	9,861	0,656	0,000
Wom	Ipuas → puas3	8,690	0,939	0,000
	Wom → wom1	2,000	0,590	0,000
	Wom → wom2	10,504	0,917	0,000
	Wom → wom3	10,225	0,474	0,000

Source: Amos SEM

4.4 Goodness of Fit Test

The results of data processing using 321 samples showed Chi-square was 352,724 with a probability of 0.061. Meanwhile, from GFI, AGFI, TLI, CFI, RMSEA and CMIN / DF respectively 0.927, 0.912, 0.951, 0.957, 0.062 and 1.463, all within the range of acceptable values. The results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Coefficient of Research Model Path

Source: Amos Output

4.5 Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing is done based on the estimated values of the research model parameters shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Hypothesis Testing

H	Hubungan	Standardized Coefficient	C.R	P	Decision
H1	Harga → Kepuasan	-0,376	3,649	0,000	accepted
H2	Harga → Wom	0,206	2,986	0,000	accepted
H3	Percaya → Kepuasan	0,478	8,152	0,000	rejected.
H4	Kualitas → Kepuasan	0,321	3,202	0,000	accepted
H5	Kualitas → Wom	0,205	2,940	0,000	accepted
H6	Kepuasan → Wom	0,238	2,827	0,000	accepted
H7	(Status * Puas) → Wom	0,109	2,000	0,000	accepted

Source: Processed data

5. Conclusions and recommendations

From the results of testing on the model in this study, able to explain the relationship between pricing strategies, trust, service quality, status in the family, satisfaction, and customer WOM, has concluded that the research model is the right model to describe pricing strategies, trust, service quality, status in the family, satisfaction, and WOM consumers travel agency pilgrimage to Umrah and Hajj. The results in this study are very important because there are stages of the influence of each factor and the construct that runs in a tiered (recursive) way, that is, the variable positively influences the satisfaction variable and consumer WOM. While variable satisfaction affects the consumer's WOM variable. The results of this study are significant contributions, especially in marketing theory, and service marketing strategies.

This research produces the following conclusions: 1). Price strategy has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. This shows that with a good pricing strategy, will encourage consumer satisfaction. So it can be concluded that the pricing strategy consisting of price discounts, payment systems, special prizes, and price suitability with benefits, if done well and always improved, consumer satisfaction of the Umrah and Umrah Hajj Pilgrimage Prosperous Travel Bureau will increase. The results of the study are in line with the findings of Yong et al. (2003); Suharno, and Farida (2017). 2). The pricing strategy has a significant effect on consumer WOM, this shows that the pricing strategy will drive consumer WOM up. So it can be concluded that the price strategy, if implemented properly and always improved, the WOM consumers of Umrah and Hajj Ikhwan Travel Prosperous Travel Bureau will increase. The results of the study are in line with the findings of Anik (2013); Faith, and Edwin (2014). 3). Trust has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. This shows that consumer confidence that exists today, can encourage consumer satisfaction. So it can be concluded that consumer trust consisting of ability, trustworthy, connected, and reliable, if done well and always improved, consumer satisfaction of the Umrah and Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera travel bureau will increase. The results of the study are in line with the findings of Soo Ho, and Choi (2018); Harumi (2016). 4). Service quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction, this shows that with good service quality, it will drive consumer satisfaction. So it can be concluded that the quality of services consisting of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, if carried out properly and always improved, the quality of service for the Umrah and Hajj Ikhwan Sejah Travel Prosperous Travel Bureau will improve. The results of the study are in line with the findings of Subaebasni et al. (2019); Yousuf (2017). 5). Quality of service has a significant effect on WOM consumers, this shows that with good service quality, it will drive up consumers WOM Umrah travel agency and Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera. The results of the study are in line with the findings of Harti (2015); Leonnard (2017). 6). Satisfaction has a significant effect on consumers' WOM, this shows that the satisfaction of consumers of the Umrah and Hajj Ikhwan Blessing Prosperous Travel Bureau that exist today, can encourage consumer WOM to rise. The results are in accordance with the findings of Taghizadeh et al. (2012); Sanjaya, and Yasa (2018). 7). Status in the family significantly moderates the relationship of satisfaction with WOM consumers Umrah travel bureau and Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera. This shows that the status of the family can moderate the relationship of satisfaction with WOM consumers Umrah travel agency and the Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera. Therefore it can be concluded that the status of a family consisting of deciders, preparers, and disposers, if carried out properly and always improved, the relationship of satisfaction with WOM consumers will increase. The results of the study are in line with the findings of Prameswari, and Anik (2010); Luis et al. (2002).

This finding brings theoretical implications that the variable price strategy has a significant positive effect on increasing consumer satisfaction, and WOM in terms of price discounts, payment systems, special prizes, and price compatibility with the benefits of the Umrah and Hajj Ikhwan Sejahtera travel agency benefits. The trust variable has a significant positive effect on increasing consumer satisfaction, and WOM in terms of (able) ability, (believable) can be trusted, (connected) connected, and (dependable) can be relied upon. Service quality variables have a significant positive effect on increasing customer satisfaction, and WOM in terms of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The variable of customer satisfaction has a significant positive effect on increasing WOM in terms of expectations, satisfaction with service, and satisfaction with travel results. The practical implications are that pricing, trust and service quality strategies can increase consumer satisfaction, which in turn will increase the WOM consumers of Umroh and Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera travel agents.

Of the three variables hypothesized to influence customer satisfaction, the dominant value is the relationship of trust to satisfaction, and the smallest value is the relationship of service quality to satisfaction. Thus, the management needs to pay attention and increase the value of service quality for participants of the Umrah and Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera trips. This can be done by providing better and innovative services than what has been done now. Provide schedule departure information in a timely manner, provide this adequate place of service, and others that make participants feel comfortable.

Given the large value of trust in consumer satisfaction, it is recommended that companies travel pilgrimage services Umrah and Hajj Ikhwan Berkah Sejahtera to always increase consumer confidence by providing education about ways of implementing a good and right pilgrimage. Share information about Umrah travel tours, and places to be visited during the pilgrimage. Implementing the process of innovation for Umrah travel on an ongoing basis. Companies also should continue to maintain, and increase consumer confidence, so that customer satisfaction is maintained and can be improved. Future studies are suggested further to examine the influence of pricing strategies, trustworthiness, and service quality on satisfaction and its impact on words of mouth which are moderated by status in the Umrah pilgrimage family by adding other variables not yet covered in this study because there are many other variables that can affect word of mouth.

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